

A MULTI-SCALE MODEL FOR THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF FIBRE-REINFORCED SILICA AEROGEL COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

In the present work, a new multi-scale model is proposed to investigate the relationship between the mechanical properties and microstructure of fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composites. The multi-scale model consists of the aerogel model in nanometers and the composite model in micrometers. The aerogel model is generated to represent the cluster structure of silica aerogels based on a modified diffusion-limited cluster aggregation (DLCA) algorithm, in which the size-dependent interactions between the primary particles are obtained from theoretical derivations. A continuum damage constitutive model is established to represent the behaviour of the silica aerogel matrix in the composite by implementing the aerogel model with the discrete element method (DEM). After that, a modified embedded element technique (EET) is proposed to generate the finite element (FE) model of the silica aerogel composite with curve fibres. This multi-scale model is used to investigate the tensile behaviour of fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composites, while a comparison with experimental results is presented. The numerical results show that the present multi-scale model can simulate the in-plane tensile behaviour of the fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composite, especially the model with a primary particle radius of 1.5nm, of which predictions agree well with the experimental results.

1 INTRODUCTION

As a type of ultra-light nanoporous materials, aerogels were first introduced by Kistler in 1931[1]. These materials are the three-dimensional assemblies of nanoparticles and have a pearl-necklace network structure [2, 3]. Among these materials, silica aerogels are the most studied and exhibit many extraordinary properties such as a high specific surface area, high porosity, low thermal conductivities, low dielectric constants, and high acoustic attenuations [4, 5]. Therefore, silica aerogels have generated huge interest in many areas including thermal and acoustic insulation, optics, catalysis, and chromatographic systems. However, the brittleness restricts their application to non-load-bearing structures. Parmenter [6] found that compression fracture strength of a silica aerogel is as low as 1MPa. Recently, high strength fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composites have been produced to be used as load-bearing parts in Thermal Protection System without sacrificing much of their thermal conductivities [7]. To extend their application, it is therefore essential to study the relationship between the mechanical properties and microstructure, including structures in nanometer and micrometer, of fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composites.

So far, mechanical properties of fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composites have been investigated in experiments [7-10]. Gao et al. [8] found a great increase in mechanical strength of ceramic-fibre-

reinforced silica aerogels, comparing with native aerogels. Yang and co-workers investigated by experiments the anisotropic property [7, 10] and creep behaviour [9] of ceramic-fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composite, which contains in-plane distributed ceramic fibres. The mechanical properties of the composite under different loading conditions and temperatures have been studied. However, few literatures report the theoretical or numerical model studies focusing on the structure-properties of the composites, based on the authors' knowledge. This is mainly because that the stiffness and strength of fibres are much higher than those of the native silica aerogels (about 100GPa vs 1MPa in Young's modulus, and about 1GPa vs 0.01MPa in tensile strength), and hence the fibres in the composites have a very high critical length. In other words, the fibres must have a high aspect ratio to reinforce the composites effectively, which results in a complex fibre network in the silica aerogel matrix [7]. Therefore, it is difficult to directly generate a 3D finite element (FE) model [11]] for fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composites. To solve the problem of modelling random fibre composites (RaFCs), Harper and co-workers [12] proposed a valuable idea of ignoring fibre intersections for the FE modelling of RaFCs, where fibres were meshed as 1-D line elements. In their papers, a 2D model was employed to analyze discontinuous carbon fibre composites; the embedded element technique (EET) [13] was used to couple fibre and matrix elements. Recently, a new technique [14] was proposed by the authors to generate 3D models for RaFCs with a high fibre aspect ratio and a high fibre volume fraction, which removes the local rigidity in general EET models.

However, the mechanical properties of aerogel matrix are poor comparing with fibres, thus the conventional techniques through coupling the 1-D fibre element and the 3-D matrix element can hardly reflect the local strain near around fibres. Besides, the structure characteristics of curve fibres can be hardly reflected in a conventional representative volume element (RVE). In this paper, we propose a new multi-scale model to investigate the tensile properties of fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composites. This multi-scale model consists of the two-level cluster structure model proposed in our primary work [15] and a composite RVE model. The former is used to determine the constitutive relation of silica aerogels based on a modified DLCA algorithm using DEM simulation and theoretical derivations with the help of molecular dynamics (MD) simulation. The latter is used to represent the structure of fibre network in the composite based on a modified EET model using FE simulation. A continuum damage constitutive model of silica aerogels is established to link the two models based on the homogenization method. The effective Young's modulus and tensile strength of fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composites are predicted using finite element analysis (FEA) by introducing the constitutive model into the aerogel matrix and the fibre-matrix interface. The predictions are compared with experimental data to verify the validity of our multi-scale model. Key conclusions are drawn in the final section.

2 MODEL DESCRIPTION

2.1 Two-level model of silica aerogels

The basic particles in our two-level model are primary particles of silica aerogels, and their properties are assumed to be the same with those of dense amorphous silica. To facilitate analysis, we assume that all primary particles have uniform radius R as in the literatures [16].

Clearly, the size of bonds or necks between primary particles has significant effects on the mechanical properties of silica. Firstly, the neck radius a_0 is determined by the geometrical size and elastic properties of primary particles as well as the property of the sol-gel solution. Then the interactions between primary particles and the deformation mechanism of particle chains can be presented. In our model, a modified elastic contact model with a finite bond size is employed to determine the contact stiffness between primary particles. Besides, we use the maximum principle stress criterion and the adhesive model of Schwarz [17] to identify the fracture of the interparticle neck. The material parameters in the particle-particle interaction model are obtained by using MD simulation. After the particle-particle interaction model is established, the microstructure of silica aerogels is generated by a modified DLCA algorithm, which is performed using DEM software PFC3D [18]. More details for the two-level model of silica aerogels have been presented in Ref. [19].

Figure 1: The generated cluster structure colored by the coordination number.

Fig. 1 shows a representative cluster structure of silica aerogels, in which the primary particle radius is 2nm and the density (ρ^*) is (with a porosity of 95%). Comparing with the atomistic models with a model length of less than 15nm [20], the model length of our cluster structure is up to 350.05nm. As shown in Fig. 1(b), the pore size is not uniform in the cluster structure; it may reach tens of nanometers among secondary particles, which is consistent with the experimental observation. In the model with a density of 0.11g/cm³, the coordination number is between 1 and 6, and the mean coordination number is about 3.10. This mean value is close to the one obtained by the model of Gelb et al. [16].

2.2 Constitutive model of aerogels matrix

As the size of the characteristic structures of silica aerogels is much smaller than that of the composite (tens of nanometers of secondary particles comparing with several micrometers of fibre's diameter) and distribute randomly in the 3D space, the silica aerogel matrix can be assumed as homogeneous and isotropic materials. The effective elastic properties of the aerogel can be expressed by two elastic constants, the effective Young's modulus E_m and the shear modulus G_m .

Based on the stress-strain relation shown in Ref. [15], the silica aerogel matrix is assumed as quasi-brittle materials in our model. Existing failure models developed for isotropic materials have been modified to reflect the change of failure mechanisms, consisting of the volumetric deformation and the distortional deformation. To reduce computations, a simple failure model expressed in the strain space has been employed as

$$\phi = \frac{I_1}{I_1^{cr}} + \left(\frac{J_2}{J_2^{cr}} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (1)$$

where $I_1 \equiv \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})$ and $J_2 \equiv [(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \mathbf{I}I_1/3) : (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \mathbf{I}I_1/3)]/2$ are respectively the first and second invariants of strain tensor. Using the tensile strength S_m^t and shear strength S_m^s , constants I_1^{cr} and J_2^{cr} can be expressed as

$$\begin{cases} I_1^{cr} = \left(\frac{1}{G_m} - \frac{1}{E_m} \right) \frac{\sqrt{3}S_m^t S_m^s}{\sqrt{3}S_m^s - S_m^t} \\ J_2^{cr} = \left(\frac{1}{2G_m} S_m^s \right)^2 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Once the failure criterion is activated, the stiffness of the materials point is gradually reduced to a small value. Considering the isotropy of silica aerogels, a scalar damage index D_m is introduced to

represent the reduction of stiffness. It is governed by the equivalent displacement $X_{eq} = I_1/I_1^{cr} + (J_2/J_2^{cr})^{1/2}$, which is defined as the same with the failure function ϕ . D_m can be expressed as

$$D_m = f(X_{eq}) \quad (3)$$

when $D_m = f(X_{eq}^0 = 1)$, the initial damage occurs in the materials point; when $D_m = f(X_{eq}^f)$, the materials point fully damages, and stiffness of that point is reduced to a small value. The functional relationship between D_m and X_{eq} depends on the stress-strain relation of aerogel matrix obtained from our two-level model, which will be discussed in Section 3.1.

Finally, the stiffness tensor of the materials point is expressed as

$$\mathbf{C}_m(D_m) = D_m \mathbf{C}_m^0 \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{C}_m^0 is the initial stiffness tensor of the silica aerogel matrix.

2.3 Composite model

To generate the complex fibre architecture in the FE model, fibres are modeling as 1-D elements to ignore the intersections between them. Fibre elements have to be linked to the matrix mesh by some approaches. Fig. 2 shows a sketch of the conventional EET technique for the linking here. The translational degrees of freedom of each fibre node are constrained to the interpolated values of the corresponding degrees of freedom of the matrix nodes. However, the stiffness and strength of fibres are much higher than those of aerogel matrix, thus the conventional model through directly linking the 1-D fibre element and the 3-D matrix element can hardly reflect the local deformation of the matrix near around fibres.

Figure 2: A sketch of linking 1-D fibre element and 3-D matrix element by embedded element technique (EET).

In our model, the EET technique has been modified to describe the interaction between the fibre and the matrix. Similar to the well accepted shear lag model, a layer of matrix around the fibre has been treated as an "interphase" to transfer the load from the matrix to the fibre through shear deformation. Experimental observation shows that the nano-sized aerogel particles are adhered to the reinforcing fibres [7]. Therefore, an assumption is made that the interphase is perfectly bonded to the reinforcing fibre. Besides, we assume that the tensile and shear deformations are decoupling in the interphase. Thus, the effective shear stiffness of the interphase can be expressed as

$$K_{int} = \frac{F}{u} = \frac{2\pi l G_m}{\ln(R/r_f)} \quad (5)$$

where $u = u_f - u_m$ is the difference between the deformation of the fibre and that of the outer matrix; G_m is the shear modulus of the matrix; l is the length of an infinitesimal segment of fibre; R and r_f are respectively the outer radius of interphase and that of fibre. Then, we assume that the fibre volume fraction can be evaluated by the two radii mentioned above as $V_f = (r_f/R)^2$. Therefore, the effective shear stiffness of the interphase should be depended on the fibre volume fraction, i.e.

$$K_{\text{int}} = \frac{-4\pi}{\ln V_f} l G_m \quad (6).$$

Moreover, the failure occurs at the position near the fibre. Therefore, equivalent failure force of the interphase can be evaluated by the shear strength S_m^s of the matrix, i.e.

$$F_{\text{int}}^{cr} = 2\pi r_f l S_m^s \quad (7).$$

In our model, link elements are employed between the fibre element and the matrix mesh to describe the behaviour of the interphase. The equivalent Young's modulus and strength of the interphase element can be expressed as

$$\begin{cases} E_{\text{int}} = c_E G_m, & c_E = \frac{-4\pi}{\ln V_f} \\ \sigma_{\text{int}}^{cr} = c_s S_m^s, & c_s = \frac{2\pi r_f}{L_{\text{int}}} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where L_{int} is the length of the link element.

Another result of the poor mechanical properties of silica aerogel matrix is that the reinforcing fibres have to be long. An algorithm [21] is employed to generate the architecture of curve fibres in the 3D space. In the present work, we only need to present the distribution of the curvature of fibre in plane. Fig. 3(a) shows the fibre distribution in the in-plane direction. Then, an approach is employed to maintain the periodicity, the treated fibre architecture in a RVE has been shown in Fig. 3(b). It is worth noting that in our models the elements describing fibres and matrix are physically overlaid on each other, introducing an approximation in terms of the phase volumes into the models. The resulting errors are minor because the stiffness of fibre is much higher than that of the matrix here.

Figure 3: Fibre architectures: (a) a randomly in-plane distribution; (b) a distribution in the RVE.

3 SIMULATIONS AND RESULTS

In this section, the present multi-scale model is employed to simulate the tensile behaviour of the fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composites. To verify the validity of our multi-scale model, the predictions are compared with the published experimental data [10]. Thus, the material parameters are all obtained from Ref. [10], which are listed in Table 1. It is worthy to note that Ref. [10] have not presented the primary particle radius R of the silica aerogel matrix. Nevertheless, the density of silica aerogel matrix can be evaluated from the fibre volume fraction, the density of the composite and that of fibres. Based on our previous study [15], the silica aerogel matrix with density of 0.116 g/cm^3 consists of the primary particles with a radius ranging from 1.0nm to 2.0nm. Therefore, three cases of $R=1.0\text{nm}$, 1.5nm , and 2.0nm are discussed in the following simulations.

Parameters for fibres		
Length	L_f (mm)	35 ± 5
Diameter	d_f (μm)	5
Density	ρ_f (g/cm^3)	2.6
Young's modulus	E_f (GPa)	170
Poisson's ratio	ν_f	0.25
Strength	S_f (GPa)	1.0
Parameters for the composite		
Fibre volume fraction	V_f (%)	7
Density	ρ_m (g/cm^3)	0.29
Parameters for the silica aerogel matrix		
Density	ρ_m (g/cm^3)	0.116
Porosity	Ψ (%)	94.7

Table 1: Summary of parameters used in the models.

3.1 Simulation of silica aerogels

The present two-level model is implemented in DEM in order to gain an insight into the fracture and deformation behaviour of the silica aerogel matrix, and to obtain the materials parameters for the models of the matrix and the interphase mentioned in Section 2. Therefore, we focus on the tensile behaviour and the shear behaviour of silica aerogels. The simulation schemes of tension and shearing are respectively shown in Fig. 4 (a) and (b), in which the numerical sample is bonded to the boundary particle aggregations. The details of the numerical model and the loading schemes are all similar to our previous work [15]. The only difference is that a shear simulation has been implemented by changing the loading direction.

Figure 4: The schematic diagrams of the numerical sample under (a) tension and (b) shear.

The simulations indicate that the shape of the stress-strain curves of silica aerogels under tension and shear are both approximately bilinear. Therefore, the relationship between the damage index D_m

and the equivalent displacement X_{eq} can be treated as

$$D_m = \frac{X_{eq}^f (X_{eq} - X_{eq}^0)}{X_{eq} (X_{eq}^f - X_{eq}^0)} \quad (9)$$

All the materials parameters obtained using the two-level model are listed in Table 2.

Primary particle radius	R (nm)	1.0	1.5	2.0
Young's modulus	E_m (MPa)	11.43	6.80	4.81
Shear modulus	G_m (MPa)	4.93	2.83	1.78
Tensile strength	S_m^t (MPa)	0.204	0.118	0.071
Shear strength	S_m^s (MPa)	0.186	0.102	0.062
Full damage equivalent displacement	X_{eq}^f	3	3	3

Table 2: Summary of parameters evaluated by using the two-level model.

3.2 Tensile response of the composite

The present composite model with modified EET is implemented in ANSYS13.0 to simulate the in-plane tensile response of the fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composite at the mesoscopic level. The 3D link elements (Link 180) are used to represent fibres. The matrix is represented by a regular array of solid elements (Solid 185). The constitutive models of the matrix and the effective "interphase" have been implemented, by means of FORTRAN user subroutines (UserMat) within ANSYS. As aforementioned, three types of cases with primary particle radius $R=1.0\text{nm}$, 1.5nm , and 2.0nm have been discussed in order to correspond with the density of the silica aerogel matrix. Considering the random distribution of fibres, five different numerical samples are generated for each case.

Figure 5: The in-plane stress-strain curves predicted by the multi-scale model compared with the experimental curves.

Fig. 5 presents the in-plane tensile stress-strain curves for these three types of numerical models;

the tensile curves in two directions from Ref. [10] are presented for a comparison. It shows that the characteristics of the numerical curves agrees well with those of the experimental curves. In the tensile process, the stress-strain curve is approximate linear at the initial stage. After that, cracks (experiment) or damage (simulation) occur firstly in some positions of the silica aerogel matrix, and propagate to the whole section perpendicular to the loading direction as the load increases. Meanwhile, fibres are pulled out from the matrix. As a result, the tensile stress-strain curve drops dramatically. As the materials parameters listed in Table 2, the effective stiffness and strength of the silica aerogel matrix decrease as the primary particle radius increases. Therefore, the in-plane mechanical properties of the composite are poorer when the primary particle radius is larger. It seems that the experimental curves fall in the region predicted by the numerical models with the primary particle radius of 1.5nm and 2.0nm. But, the former is closer by contrast.

In order to indicate the effect of the primary particle radius clearly, the effective in-plane Young's modulus and strength are presented in Fig. 6. The black dash dot lines and the red short dash lines respectively represent the Young's modulus and tensile strength reported in experimental literature [10]. Here, the effective Young's moduli of the numerical models are defined as the initial slopes of the stress-strain curves, where the peak value is the strength. The same definitions will be used in the following discussion. Fig. 6 clearly shows that the effective in-plane Young's modulus and the strength both decrease as the primary particle radius increases. The experimental results fall in the range of the numerical predictions. Moreover, the predictions of the models with the primary particle radius of 1.5nm are close to the experimental results

Figure 6: The effect of the primary particle size on the tensile properties of the fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composite compared with the experimental results.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a multi-scale model is proposed to investigate the effect of the microstructure on the tensile properties of fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composites. This multi-scale model mainly comprises the silica aerogel model in nanometers and the composite model in micrometers, while a continuum damage constitutive model of silica aerogels is established to link the above models in different sizes. In the silica aerogel model, the size-dependent interactions between primary particles are obtained from theoretical derivations, where the material parameters are obtained using MD simulation. Then, the cluster structure model is generated to represent the microstructure of silica aerogels based on a modified DLCA algorithm. Using DEM simulation, the tensile and shear behaviour of silica aerogels is determined by combining the particle-particle interaction model with the cluster structure model. The numerical results reveal the quasi-brittle characteristic of silica aerogels, and hence a continuum damage constitutive model is established to represent the silica

aerogel matrix in the composite model. After that, we generate the composite model by using a modified EET to reflect the characteristics of the curve fibres in the aerogel composite.

Based on FE simulation, the tensile behaviour of fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composites is determined by implementing the continuum constitutive models of silica aerogel in the composite model. The numerical results show that the tensile properties of fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composites are significantly dependent on the primary particle size. Silica aerogels with larger primary particles have lower elastic modulus and strength, and hence the corresponding composites have lower Young's modulus and tensile strength. A comparison has been conducted between the numerical results and the published experimental results. It shows that the present multi-scale model can simulate the in-plane tensile behaviour of fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composites, especially the model with a primary particle radius of 1.5nm, of which predictions agree well with the experimental results.

In a conclusion, the present multi-scale model provides an alternative theoretical-numerical approach to both the elastic and strength properties of fibre-reinforced silica aerogel composites. Furthermore, the multi-scale model can be extended to study the mechanical properties of other aerogel composites.

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